

Enabling Global FAIR Data: WorldFAIR Policy Recommendations for Research Infrastructures

This document presents the policy recommendations from the WorldFAIR project. It synthesises the project's findings and presents recommendations for specific stakeholders, for the European Open Science Cloud and other Research Infrastructures globally.

To meet the challenges and opportunities confronting 21st century science, including the need to support interdisciplinary research and the impact of AI, it calls for a shift to a data engineering approach and for investment in metadata uplift and the implementation of the FAIR principles to enable this.

WorldFAIR Policy Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Data Engineering

Policy makers and funders need to encourage and enable a data engineering approach in the data infrastructures that are the most important to address major societal and planetary challenges. Specifically, this requires supporting long lasting data aggregation and data integration services as part of EOSC and globally.

Recommendation 2: Metadata uplift

Sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata are a precondition for the data products that are essential for high priority research areas. Research infrastructures and data infrastructures need to put into practice 'metadata uplift'. They must be enabled to do so by policy makers and funders.

Recommendation 3: Interdisciplinary research for global challenges

There is a need for investment in technologies and approaches that facilitate data aggregation and data integration for interdisciplinary, grand challenge research areas. Such investment should prioritise work that automates the integration approach and allows it to be performed year on year with time series data.

Recommendation 4: Reproducible and transparent research

The global data stewardship and metadata standards community should direct concerted effort to refine and improve standards for describing data provenance and processing, as well as technologies that enable such standards to be used to provide a full and machine-actionable account of data lineage. Such work should be enabled by funders and policy makers.

Recommendation 5: Increasingly automated and controlled access to sensitive data

In partnership with the global data stewardship and metadata standards community, data services looking after sensitive data should direct concerted effort to developing and implementing systems that can support negotiation of access to data in a dynamic and more automated way. This effort should be supported by funders and policy makers.

Recommendation 6: Responsible use of AI

AI technologies (particularly generative tools based on LLMs) present a number of challenges, notably the potential misuse of sensitive information, a lack of transparency and reproducibility, and the risk of hallucinations and imprecision. The use of detailed, accurate and structured metadata should be explored as one of the means of enhancing the utility and precision of these technologies and to help in imposing guardrails.

Recommendation 7: Support the further development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)

Given the pressing need for a data engineering approach to support interdisciplinary research, policy makers and funders should enable the further development of CDIF and its extension to more profiles and recommendations. The data stewardship community, metadata standards organisations and data infrastructures should collaborate to implement, test, refine and improve the current and forthcoming CDIF profiles and recommendations.

Recommendation 8: Invest in Research Infrastructures

Research infrastructures should be encouraged and enabled to transition to a data engineering approach and provide researchers with pre-integrated, ‘science-ready’, interdisciplinary data products. This will require investment to build capacity and to adopt new technologies and approaches. This transition should be enabled by funders and policy makers. It should be embraced by research infrastructures and data repositories as a necessary evolution of their function and mission.

Recommendation 9.1: Enable standards bodies and international and representative organisations

To advance FAIR implementation, it is important to take a multi-stakeholder approach. In particular, policy makers and funders should help support the role played by representative and authoritative organisations as well as standards bodies on an international scale.

Recommendation 9.2: Support WorldFAIR+

The WorldFAIR approach should be further tested and refined as a means of enabling research communities to develop and implement good practice, through a multi-stakeholder approach. Policy makers and funders should support the WorldFAIR+ initiative and similar activities.

Recommendation 9.3: Support the FIPs approach and infrastructure

Funders and policy makers, through investment and appropriate policy direction, should support the global data stewardship community to socialise the FIPs approach, and to improve and sustain the necessary infrastructures.

Recommendation 9.4: Support CODATA and RDA to enable research communities

The Research Data Alliance and CODATA should be supported in their activities to enable research disciplines and interdisciplinary research areas to advance their FAIR practices.

Recommendation 10: Support the sustainability of semantic artefacts

Policy makers and funders should help to ensure the sustainability of the standards organisations that develop and maintain metadata schema, terminologies, and other semantic artefacts. An immediate step would be to fund a project to conduct survey and analysis of business models, governance and juridical status, and make recommendations to improve the sustainability and effectiveness of such organisations.

Recommendation 11: Strengthen international partnerships

EOSC should actively build international partnerships with standards bodies, inter-governmental initiatives and global representative bodies. Contributing to the development of a strong global ecosystem for data and metadata exchange will benefit EOSC and is necessary for its success.

WorldFAIR: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice

‘WorldFAIR: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice’¹ was a two-year project to advance implementation of the FAIR principles², particularly in relation to interoperability and reusability of data, within and across research domains. The project had genuinely global scope, and an explicit mission to advance global collaboration and included partners from outside the European Union³. WorldFAIR was coordinated by CODATA⁴, the Committee on Data of the International Science Council⁵, with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) association⁶ as a major partner. As well as these two international data organisations, WorldFAIR involved (either directly as beneficiaries, or indirectly through partner organisations) a number of authoritative and representative international projects, organisations, initiatives or infrastructures (e.g. NanoCommons⁷, OneGeochemistry⁸, SALURBAL⁹, GBIF¹⁰, ODIS¹¹), as well as standards-setting organisations with global scope (e.g. IUPAC¹², DDI Alliance¹³, OHDSI¹⁴, TDWG¹⁵).

The project was conceived as responding to Recommendation 4 of the ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ report, which identified the need to ‘Develop interoperability frameworks for FAIR sharing within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research’. The Recommendation states that ‘Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure. To support interdisciplinary research, these interoperability frameworks should be articulated

in common ways and adopt global standards where relevant.’¹⁶ As well as the international dimension, it is this vision of enabling community agreements around interoperability, and encouraging the identification and adoption of common standards, that drove the WorldFAIR project.

WorldFAIR worked with a set of eleven domain and cross-domain case studies¹⁷, carefully chosen from existing CODATA and RDA activities or partnerships to provide maximum impact. Each case study (in project terms, a ‘Work Package’) developed an interoperability framework, comprising recommendations and/or a FAIR implementation for their discipline or interdisciplinary research area. Led by CODATA, a coordinating and synthesis activity (Work Package 2) supported each case study in understanding their requirements through the completion of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). In turn these insights were incorporated into the development of a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) and recommendations for future work on domain-sensitive FAIR guidelines and assessment.

Consequently, the perspective of the WorldFAIR project is avowedly global and holds that the EC, the European Research Area and EOSC have a major role to play as part of an international science ecosystem. It is firmly in the interest of the EU, and essential to the success of EOSC, to contribute positively to international data infrastructures, to international standards development, and the implementation of good practices as recommended in the CDIF.

1 <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

2 Wilkinson, M., et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

3 WorldFAIR included partners from the following countries: Belgium, Cyprus, Denmark, Germany, France, Ireland (EU); Norway (outside EU but eligible for Horizon framework funding); Australia, Brazil, Kenya, New Zealand, USA (outside EU and not usually eligible for EU funding); UK (at the start of the WorldFAIR project, the UK institutions were not eligible for EU funding).

4 <https://codata.org/>

5 <https://council.science/>

6 <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>

7 <https://www.nanocommons.eu/>

8 <https://onegeochemistry.github.io/>

9 <https://drexel.edu/lac/salurbal/overview/>

10 <https://www.gbif.org/>

11 <https://odis.iode.org/>

12 <https://iupac.org/>

13 <https://ddialliance.org/>

14 <https://www.ohdsi.org/>

15 <https://www.tdwg.org/>

16 European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Turning FAIR into Reality: final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>; p. 29.

17 <https://worldfair-project.eu/case-studies-of-worldfair/>

Policy Issues: evidence, analysis and recommendations

FAIR Data for 21st Century Science

The WorldFAIR policy recommendations reflect an international perspective, and a conviction regarding the need to orchestrate data internationally, to provide global scientific endeavours with the data needed to help address the planetary and societal challenges of the 21st Century. Science has an essential role in providing the evidence needed for effective policy-making and sustainable interventions. Open science and the FAIR principles are two related practices that can enable science to realise the opportunities afforded by the digital era. For this to be the case, transformations in scientific culture, methodologies, institutions, infrastructures and engagement with society are needed¹⁸. In this policy brief, we are primarily concerned with the necessary transformations that relate to the implementation of the FAIR principles as a means to equip scientific communities with the tools, infrastructure and data needed to pursue their mission in these changing circumstances, defined by the opportunities and affordances created by digital transformations.

1. Data Engineering

There is an urgent need for a shift from a ‘bibliographic’ data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice! The most fundamental recommendation to emerge from the WorldFAIR project is the following: to support the requirements of 21st Century science, we need to enable a transformation in our practice for data stewardship

and move from a bibliographic approach to a data engineering approach.

In the bibliographic model, data is treated like a book in a library: a dataset is deposited in an appropriate domain specialist or generalist repository as a data package, with a persistent identifier and discovery metadata in an extended form of Dublin Core. This is, of course, better than nothing: the repository and the data stewards involved have performed an important service in ensuring that the data was not (to all intents and purposes) lost on a research group server or a personal hard drive. For such data to be reused, however, the dataset must be downloaded, and the significant task of data wrangling remains, often with inadequate, non-standard or only implicit information about the data and semantics. This is precisely the issue highlighted in the PWC report on the opportunity costs of not having FAIR data¹⁹, and it falls well short of the EOSC and FAIR vision of machine-actionable data. If we persist with the bibliographic model, we will not achieve the ‘web of FAIR data and services’ promised by the EOSC.

In a seminal 2012 article ‘Is Data Publication the Right Metaphor?’²⁰, Parsons and Fox drew our attention to this precise issue. Unfortunately, the ‘data publication’ or bibliographic model still dominates how we think about data stewardship, research data management, and the role of data repositories. A related issue is made clear by the WorldFAIR case studies and elsewhere: in many research fields too much effort and expense are still going into extracting data, *ex post facto*, from academic articles or supplementary materials²¹.

18 These necessary transformations are well documented in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

19 The PWC report for the European Commission estimated the opportunity cost of not having FAIR data to be 10.2 Bn per annum. The report also estimated that ‘data cleansing’ or data wrangling of

poor quality data ‘can take up to 80% of the total effort’, leaving only 20% of project effort for analysis. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Cost-benefit analysis for FAIR research data: cost of not having FAIR research data, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/02999>

20 Parsons, M.A. and Fox, P.A. (2013) ‘Is Data Publication the Right Metaphor?’, Data

Science Journal, 12(0), p. WDS32-WDS46. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2481/dsj.WhgDS-042>.

21 In WorldFAIR, this is the case in a number of the research areas involved, but was particularly remarked on by the nanomaterials, geochemistry, biodiversity and plant-pollinator case studies.

Data compilations are essential for effective research in many domains. At present, such efforts are hampered by numerous barriers. In many research areas (e.g. nanomaterials, plant-pollinator interactions) an astonishing amount of effort goes into the compilation of data extracted laboriously from published articles²². Consequently, essential data is often behind paywalls, and even more often communicated in formats that require a great deal of manual intervention. Such data should be deposited directly into the data aggregator as part of the workflow for making available (‘publishing’) the outputs from research and funded projects, and should be sufficiently well-described to support further use.

A significant part of the inefficiencies and opportunity costs identified in the PWC report, come from insufficient data stewardship, and they are left unaddressed by the data management involved in the bibliographic model. Quite simply, the use case in which researchers deposit data in support of their publication is not the only, or the most important, use case.

In the data engineering model, by contrast, data are treated as collections of ‘datums’ (individual data points, measurements, observations, annotations etc), each of which has sufficient associated information to be treated independently if necessary. This is what allows the selection of certain variables of interest, and their recombination with other variables in an aggregated resource or a new data product for analysis. In many fields, it is essential to integrate data from multiple sources to build up data on a topic globally to provide the evidence needed for well-grounded science and policy interventions.

Such data engineering is metadata-intensive and aims to create a network of (FAIR) data exchange. We understand the aspiration of EOSC to achieve a ‘web of FAIR data and services’ in precisely these terms. A good example of metadata facilitating a (relatively FAIR) data exchange is the use of SDMX²³

in the statistical and economic regulatory sector. Another example is GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, which serves as the world’s resource for biodiversity and species occurrence data²⁴. Faced with an increasing variety of new data sources (including most notably environmental DNA and camera trap data), GBIF has been obliged to develop a new Unified Model that allows the integration of such data²⁵. Another highly pertinent example is ODIS²⁶, the Ocean Data Information System, which uses an agreed architecture and a knowledge graph approach to federate data globally²⁷. The data engineering paradigm is also evident in the work of INSPIRE to combine population health data with clinical outcome data, for research and policy uses²⁸.

The shift from a bibliographic approach to a data engineering approach is one of a magnitude which will necessitate considerable resourcing, investment, and upskilling, but which will also achieve significant benefits. The objective of such a shift is to provide a network for FAIR data exchange which will help to realise the opportunities noted above: automated data combination for cross-domain research and automated and fine-grained access control, ultimately better enabling the use of AI.

This cultural change will be a difficult one; nor is there likely to be a sufficient balance of cost-to-benefit for such an approach to be applied to all data, all the time. But we are witnessing increasing demand for research infrastructures to respond to the challenges described above. The use case that led to SDMX, GBIF and ODIS is pressing in many other research fields. Were this not the case, we would not see so many projects performing *ex post facto* extraction of data from research articles!

Furthermore, the energy, willingness, and requirement to undertake this transformation exists as a result of the FAIR vision, and it is one of the objectives of the Open Science movement and EOSC. Thus, from a policy perspective, we are faced with both significant challenges and a significant opportunity.

22 Drucker, D.P., et al. (2024). WorldFAIR (D10.2) ‘Agricultural Biodiversity Standards, Best Practices and Guidelines Recommendations’ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666593>, pp. 9-34, p. 26.

23 Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange - <https://sdmx.org/>

24 CODATA, the Committee on Data of the ISC, Pfeiffenberger, H., Uhlir, P., & Hodson, S. (2020). Twenty-Year Review of GBIF. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.35035/ctzm-hz97>;

25 D9.2; <https://worldfair-project.eu/biodiversity/>

26 <https://odis.iode.org/>

27 <https://worldfair-project.eu/ocean-science-sustainable-development/>

28 <https://worldfair-project.eu/population-health/>

Recommendation 1: Data Engineering.

Policy makers and funders need to encourage and enable a data engineering approach in the data infrastructures that are the most important to address major societal and planetary challenges. Specifically, this requires supporting long-lasting data aggregation and data integration services as part of EOSC and globally.

2. Metadata Uplift

An essential component of data engineering is the addition of **sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata**. To be crystal clear, here we are not referring simply to the metadata that enables discoverability, that helps address ‘Findable’ in the FAIR principles. We are referring to those components of metadata schema that facilitate interoperability, enabling data to be combined, integrated and reused. This includes, but is not limited to, definitions of variables (or quantities), descriptions of data structure, provenance and processing information²⁹. DDI-CDI³⁰ and the draft CDIF profiles³¹ provide examples of how this can be put into practice in cross-domain scenarios. In the DDI community, the term ‘metadata uplift’ has been coined to describe the task of adding sufficient information to facilitate analysis across datasets, and includes explorations of the use of machine learning (ML) to support that task³².

For data to be (re-)used in research (i.e. compared, combined, analysed) the information about the data needs to be very detailed. The scientist — and their analytical tools — need to know what **may** be done

with the data, and they need to know what **can** be done with the data. Cascading from this, knowing how the data can be processed, combined, and analysed requires — as a minimum — information about the concepts, variables and units involved, the data structure, the provenance and processing the data may have undergone, and estimates of their quality and accuracy. The increasing scale and complexity of research questions require an increasing scale of data stewardship and ‘metadata uplift’.

While much attention is paid to artificial intelligence (AI) as the most important emerging technology, the factor which most limits its use, at least in science, is a mundane one: **research data that are not sufficiently described cannot be used by any form of intelligence, artificial or otherwise**. Much of the effort that goes into AI approaches, in relation to scientific discovery, is only necessary because the provenance and detail regarding the research data being consumed have been discarded after the initial data collection or generation. Good data stewardship, which preserves and publishes this detailed information about the data, will enable powerful AI techniques to realise their promise more fully, and support more effective use of traditional data analysis approaches as well.

Recommendation 2: Metadata Uplift.

Sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata are a precondition for the data products that are essential for high priority research areas. Research infrastructures and data infrastructures need to put into practice ‘metadata uplift’. They must be enabled to do so by policy makers and funders.

²⁹ Here we employ the broad definition of ‘metadata’ that is accepted in many contexts and research disciplines. We recognise that some research fields think of these things (which include controlled vocabularies, ontologies, data models) as semantic artefacts, or as part of the data. We do not want to open this particular Pandora’s box of terminological discord, but need to

be clear that we are employing the term ‘metadata’ in its broadest sense.

³⁰ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

³¹ Gregory, A., et al. (2024). WorldFAIR (D2.3) ‘Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)’ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871>

³² <https://ddialliance.org/metadata-uplift-%E2%80%93-pdfexcel-to-structured-ddi-documentation>; see also SRIA 1.2, p. 162 https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

There are four drivers for this call for data engineering and ‘metadata uplift’. These are addressed in the following four recommendations and include:

1. Interdisciplinary research for global challenges;
2. Reproducible and transparent research;
3. Responsible use of AI in science;
4. Increasingly automated controlled access to sensitive data.

3. Interdisciplinary Research for Global Challenges

The major global human, societal, environmental and scientific challenges of our age are fundamentally interdisciplinary and related to all sectors of society. These challenges can only be addressed through the close collaboration of science, civil society, and government using cross-domain and multi-stakeholder research that seeks to understand complex systems through machine-assisted analysis, and enables data-driven decision-making processes³³. The ability to combine data across traditional disciplines is becoming a *sine qua non* for many areas of research.

As argued above, this requires a shift to data engineering, enabled by the collaborative development, refinement and international adoption of sufficiently detailed, fine-grained, standardised, and interoperable metadata. Some examples of this have been provided above. Another is the EOSC Future ‘Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities’ Project³⁴ which combined European Social Survey data with climate and air quality data to create an important resource for understanding the relation of attitudes to climate change and environmental degradation based on lived experience. Notable about this work was the use of DDI-CDI, a CDIF component, to provide valuable information to researchers and data scientists about the way in which compound variables have been constructed.

Data wrangling to create integrated data sets is frequently conducted as a one-off, labour intensive, manual process. The data engineering approach, and the call for ‘sufficiently detailed, standardised, and interoperable metadata’, seeks to establish the preconditions for such effort to be increasingly automated and repeated year on year for time series data. Doing so also with sufficient metadata about provenance and processing is foundational for reproducibility of findings and transparency.

Recommendation 3: Interdisciplinary Research for Global Challenges.

There is a need for investment in technologies and approaches that facilitate data aggregation and data integration for interdisciplinary, grand challenge research areas. Such investment should prioritise work that automates the integration approach and allows it to be performed year on year with time series data.

4. Reproducible and Transparent Research

Concerns about the reproducibility and replicability of scientific results have many dimensions. Although there are disputes about the scale of the ‘crisis’ and the way the phenomenon itself has been studied, perceptions that there *is* a crisis³⁵ are sufficiently strong for national and international initiatives to be launched to improve practice³⁶. Universal application of the requirement that data be deposited in an appropriate repository — as a condition of publication — would help address a part of the issue³⁷. Where such services exist in specific research fields, data should be deposited in a recognised regional or international data aggregator, or in a local or national service that can be harvested internationally³⁸.

33 See for example, the International Science Council’s Action Plan, area 2.1: <https://council.science/actionplan/making-data-work-for-grand-challenges/>

34 <https://eoscfuture.eu/data/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities/>

35 Baker, M. 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. *Nature* 533, 452–454 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>

36 <https://www.ukrn.org/global-networks/>

37 Miyakawa, T. No raw data, no science: another possible source of the reproducibility crisis. *Molecular Brain*, 13,

24 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13041-020-0552-2>

38 Drucker, D. P. et al. (2024). WorldFAIR (D10.3) ‘Agricultural biodiversity FAIR data assessment rubrics’ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719265>, p. 24-5.

Additionally, through the data engineering approach described above and explored in WorldFAIR, it is possible (in principle) to provide improved and more automated documentation of provenance and data lineage. Such information does not just pertain to how the data were created, but also to capturing — in machine-readable and machine-actionable ways — any processing (e.g. normalisation, data reduction), integration and combination with other data, and analysis. To enable reuse, and to ensure transparency and reproducibility, it is important to be able to document (automatically) all the transformations data have undergone, as well as the methodologies, reasoning and logical steps used to arrive at conclusions.

Standards for describing data provenance — including PROV-O³⁹, the Common Workflow Language (CWL)⁴⁰, DDI-CDI Process descriptions⁴¹, Validation and Transformation Language (VTL)⁴², and Structured Data Transformation Language (SDTL)⁴³ — are all primarily descriptions of a stepwise process, involving actors, input/outputs, and processing actions. Shortcomings are encountered because the outputs of research are frequently used as inputs to further research, but the description of provenance (when it exists) is limited to a description of each stage in isolation. It is almost never the case that we can find a full description of data lineage using the existing standard models: they are implemented in a limited way, describing (typically) a single step in the chain. Existing models are insufficient for a complete description of data lineage, making it unrealistic to expect that data providers and users could provide this information. The need to connect such descriptions with each other to provide a fuller and machine-actionable summary of data lineage is emerging as an important area for attention.

Recommendation 4: Reproducible and Transparent Research.

The global data stewardship and metadata standards community should direct concerted effort to refine and improve standards for describing data provenance and processing, as well as technologies that enable such standards to be used to provide a full and machine-actionable account of data lineage. Such work should be enabled by funders and policy makers.

5. Increasingly Automated and Controlled Access to Sensitive Data

In many circumstances, access to data must be controlled. For many data archives, the manual management of access is a considerable time burden. Where this can be safely automated, efficiency benefits are achieved. A further related use case for the data engineering approach and increased automation is that of providing more fine-grained access to data sets (which may contain some sensitive data), and thereby addressing pressing issues of organisational and legal interoperability.

In systems in which entire files, or collections of files, are the object to which access rights are assigned, the ‘access boundary’ is necessarily limited to letting the most confidential and/or sensitive variables determine the access level to the whole package. For example, if we have a file containing 200 variables, of which two contain potentially sensitive, personal or disclosive information, then the entire file must be ruled off-limits for those who do not have sufficient access privileges. This phenomenon is termed ‘data poisoning’: that is, 198 of the 200 variables must be restricted (quarantined) for many legitimate users because of the ‘toxic’, disclosive nature of only two variables and through which they have been ‘infected’. The real-world consequences of this are increased access times to data for end-users, and complex administrative overheads for

39 <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

40 <https://www.commonwl.org/>

41 <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

42 https://sdmx.org/?page_id=5096

43 <https://ddialliance.org/products/sdtl/1.0>

data providers, with locally defined, often human-mediated workflows, which cannot scale up in the long term. **A significant limiting factor, therefore, is the inability to automate the negotiation of data access, which — while difficult — has been shown to be feasible in cases where sufficiently granular metadata exists.**

What we can understand from this is that the existing culture of data management, which often views the ‘data set’ as a monolithic entity acting as an adjunct to the publications it underpins, is a barrier to secondary data use. The data engineering approach, in which sets of datums, or selected variables, have sufficient associated information to be treated independently, provides a solution.

Some interesting steps along these lines are being taken in relation to the automation of access control, although these are less well developed. The UK Data Archive and others have been exploring how approaches borrowed from other domains can be combined with efforts in the world of research data to help make the granting of access to data more efficient, and also more ‘focused’ (that is, to be more permissive where ‘data poisoning’ has traditionally presented a barrier to access)⁴⁴. These efforts show us that in order to automate access control, fine-grained management of data — at the variable level — as well as machine-actionable descriptions of the access conditions and roles and qualifications of the users given access, must be implemented.

It is a legal and moral imperative that access to data be granted in an ethical manner, in line with accepted best practice. At the same time, these obligations should not present any greater barrier to reuse of data than necessary. The key to finding the right balance — to increasing legal and organisational interoperability — is to have granular access control, so that data access can be as broad as possible, and no broader. Systems that can support negotiation of access to data in a dynamic and more automated way are needed to responsibly meet the demand for data while also generating efficiency benefits for data services.

Recommendation 5: Increasingly Automated and Controlled Access to Sensitive Data.

In partnership with the global data stewardship and metadata standards community, data services looking after sensitive data should direct concerted effort to developing and implementing systems that can support negotiation of access to data in a dynamic and more automated way. This effort should be supported by funders and policy makers.

6. Responsible Use of AI

Many of the same issues are relevant for the responsible use of AI in science. There is a lot of noise and churn on this topic, but the issues may be summarised as follows:

1. How may we best avoid the misuse of (sensitive) information in Large Language Models (LLMs) and other forms of AI?
2. How can we maximise transparency and reproducibility in results obtained using AI?
3. How may we best reduce the risk of hallucinations and imprecision?

How may we best avoid the misuse of (sensitive) information in LLMs and other forms of AI?

The emergence of LLMs and generative AI have added extra complexity and potential risk to the issues described above in relation to sensitive data. The concerns are twofold: first, that the new technologies increase the risk, for example, of accidental disclosure and identification; and second, that the increased risk will make organisations more risk-averse and throttle progress on machine accessibility to data.

⁴⁴ Lungley, Deidre, Gilders, Thomas, Bell, Darren, & Rumiancev, Artiom. (2022, November 30). Towards Machine-assisted Disclosure Assessment with DDI-CDI, DPV and sdeMicro. EDDI2022: The 14th Annual European DDI User Conference (EDDI2022), Sciences Po, Paris, France. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7656053>

It is always important to describe what the data can be used for, and who is allowed to use it. When machines become an important class of data users — especially at the scale of LLMs — it is essential that the terms of use, and the qualifications required for use, be made available to them in a machine-actionable fashion. For research infrastructures, particularly those dealing with sensitive data, it will be important to explore the extent to which contracts, licences, the criteria for access, the qualifications of the potential user, and the legislation that underpins each of these things, can be made machine-actionable. There is currently no good way to describe terms and conditions of use for data in a standard, machine-actionable way, although frameworks such as the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)⁴⁵ are a promising start, as is work such as the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)⁴⁶, both from W3C. Neither is sufficient to meet the current challenge, however, in their current form. Further work is necessary on this topic⁴⁷.

How can we maximise transparency and reproducibility in results obtained using AI?

The shortcomings of current models to describe data lineage and the need for further work on this topic has been described above. AI — and LLM-based generative AI in particular — makes this situation even worse. These technologies present us with ‘black boxes’ which do not act in a stepwise fashion suitable for description using typical approaches. There is no visibility into the process other than through an examination of the algorithms and the code which implements it, informed by a knowledge of the training set used. Such information is rarely available⁴⁸.

The DDI-CDI process model may help in this regard and indicate a useful direction for further work. The model supports the case where the inputs, success criteria, and a ‘playbook’ of functions can be described, along with the processing engine. This information then becomes part of the provenance description attached to the resulting data. While still not providing visibility into the operations

of the black box, it does give a reasonable set of information for use in determining who did what to any given set of data.

How may we best reduce the risk of hallucinations and imprecision? ‘Hallucinations’ are a sufficiently known phenomenon with generative AI, for the term to have become a commonplace. More dangerous are those cases where an unknown degree of imprecision applies to results which seem plausible on the surface. The key point of discussion here tends to be around the data used to train LLMs and other AI models. Within the FAIR community, discussions are underway to explore how a better description of data, along the lines of the FAIR Principles, can help to protect society from the worst tendencies of AI, by diminishing the likelihood of hallucinations and imprecision⁴⁹. Google and others have been developing the Croissant⁵⁰ specification for providing metadata descriptions of training data sets: these models are similar to (but semantically poorer than) the DDI-CDI standard advocated in CDIF, but they are currently compatible (generating a Croissant description from a DDI-CDI one would be relatively trivial). The idea that accurate, structured metadata could help reduce imprecision and hallucination does, however, appear to be a sound assumption and worthy of further exploration.

Recommendation 6: Responsible Use of AI.

AI technologies (particularly generative tools based on LLMs) present a number of challenges, notably the potential misuse of sensitive information, a lack of transparency and reproducibility, and the risk of hallucinations and imprecision. The use of detailed, accurate and structured metadata should be explored as one of the means of enhancing the utility and precision of these technologies and to help in imposing guardrails.

45 <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

46 <https://www.w3.org/community/dpvcg/>

47 Rouchon, O., et al. (2024). D6.2 - Core metadata schema for legal interoperability <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11104269> for a discussion of some of these issues and a survey of metadata profiles.

48 Research is moving rapidly. Approaches are being explored through which it can be indicated when specific nodes within the knowledge graph driving the LLM have been used in the response to a prompt: <https://arxiv.org/html/2312.16374v2>.

49 <https://www.lorenzcenter.nl/the-road-to-fair-and-equitable-science.html>

50 Akhtar, M, et al., (2024), ‘Croissant: A Metadata Format for ML-Ready Datasets’ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.19546>

The remaining recommendations outline actions to enable data engineering and metadata uplift, and provide the tools to respond to the challenges in the four drivers just discussed.

7. Support the Further Development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)

The CDIF idea emerges from several years of discussion and related work and is conceived as a set of recommendations for the coordinated use of standards to enable automated, cross-domain sharing of data and metadata. By establishing a ‘lingua franca’ based on existing cross-domain standards, it will become possible to implement cross-domain exchange of FAIR metadata and data – including data discovery, access, and integration – in a scalable fashion. In the simplest terms, CDIF is a compilation of recommended practices for implementing relevant standards, to support the needed interchange of data and metadata. The first set of CDIF modules⁵¹ make recommendations for the use of cross-domain standards and practices for 1) discovery (of data and metadata resources); 2) data access (specifically, machine-actionable descriptions of access conditions and permitted use); 3) controlled vocabularies (good practices for the publication of controlled vocabularies and semantic artefacts); 4) data integration (description of the structural and semantic aspects of data to make it integration-ready); and 5) universals (the description of ‘universal’ elements, time, geography, and units of measurement). Five areas of future work are also discussed: i) provenance (the description of provenance and processing); ii) context (the description of ‘context’ in the form of dependencies between fields within the data and a description of the research setting); iii) AI (discussing the impacts of AI and the role that metadata can play); iv) packaging (the creation of archival and dissemination packages); v) additional Data Formats (support for some of the data formats not fully supported in the initial release, such as NetCDF⁵², Parquet⁵³, and HDF⁵⁴).

A number of projects to implement and test the CDIF recommendations are underway, scheduled or planned (notably under the banner of WorldFAIR+). We invite collaboration and feedback to refine, improve and extend the CDIF profiles and recommendations.

Recommendation 7: Support the Further Development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

Given the pressing need for a data engineering approach to support interdisciplinary research, policy makers and funders should enable the further development of CDIF and its extension to more profiles and recommendations. The data stewardship community, metadata standards organisations and data infrastructures should collaborate to implement, test, refine and improve the current and forthcoming CDIF profiles and recommendations.

8. Invest in Research Infrastructures

The proposed shift from a ‘bibliographic’ data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice is one of magnitude which will require considerable resourcing, investment, and upskilling; but it is one which will also achieve significant benefits. Increasingly, one of the principal roles of research infrastructures will be to provide researchers with pre-integrated, ‘science-ready’, interdisciplinary data products.

Few research infrastructures are currently equipped to face this task. Concern will understandably be expressed by many data archives and repositories that are under-resourced even for the current tasks of providing file-level metadata and digital preservation. By the same token, there is clearly considerable demand for this transformation and ambition on the part of many research infrastructures to be able to combine datasets for interdisciplinary research.

51 Gregory, A., Bell, D., Brickley, D., Buttigieg, P. L., Cox, S., Edwards, M., Doug, F., Gonzalez Morales, L. G., Heus, P., Hodson, S., Kanjala, C., Le Franc, Y., Maxwell,

L., Molloy, L., Richard, S., Rizzolo, F., Winstanley, P., & Wyborn, L. (2024). WorldFAIR (D2.3) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871>

52 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NetCDF>

53 <https://parquet.apache.org/>

54 <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

An excellent example of this, already mentioned above, is the EOSC Future ‘Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities’ project⁵⁵. While a part of this project looked at the detailed aspects of data integration with data coming from different sources, it also examined the organisational and scientific aspects of collaboration. Research infrastructures collaborate in what is too often an ad hoc fashion, with no planning around what other data resources could most usefully be combined with their own from a scientific perspective. This lack of preparation is seen in how resources are allocated, and how scientific projects are supported. It may not be reasonable to expect a domain-focused data repository to address cross-domain requirements, but there is a need for a collaborative framework which will make organisational and scientific collaboration a more normal part of their functioning⁵⁶.

Such cross-domain and cross-infrastructure collaboration is not possible unless the data to be integrated is well-described in the manner suggested above: the data engineering approach is a precondition for making collaborative interdisciplinary science practical. In fact, much of the technology needed for more granular data management already exists. Many data archives have implemented ‘shopping basket’ applications where researchers can select a set of variables from across the various data sets held by the archive, and such implementations reflect a change in the way these technologies are implemented rather than a shift in the underlying technology.

This change is characterised by data management at the variable level, instead of solely focusing on the data set as a monolithic entity. Within WorldFAIR, we can see this in practice in the SALURBAL case⁵⁷, in the INSPIRE Network case⁵⁸, and elsewhere. Many data infrastructures are beginning to provide this type of capability (e.g. ODIS⁵⁹ and GBIF⁶⁰ which are also partners in the WorldFAIR project).

Given the preceding observations, it is essential to insist on two points. First, the transition from bibliographic data stewardship to data engineering categorically should not place an extra burden on researchers. On the contrary, this transition, if realised, will reduce that burden. Second, those infrastructures and data services that are involved in providing researchers with data (e.g. large facilities, planetary observing systems, social surveys and so on) should be adequately resourced to provide FAIR data, to serve fully integrated data products that correspond to researchers’ needs. It is through sufficient and ambitious resourcing and implementation of a data engineering approach described here that we can address the opportunity cost of not having FAIR data and reduce the amount of effort spent on data wrangling. The same applies to the so-called ‘long tail’ of research data production, including data creation or collection activities in research performing organisations, from large faculties to individual researchers: the objective should not be to turn researchers into data stewards, but to make it easier for data stewards to furnish researchers with the data they need for analysis and knowledge creation.

Recommendation 8: Invest in Research Infrastructures.

Research infrastructures should be encouraged and enabled to transition to a data engineering approach and provide researchers with pre-integrated, ‘science-ready’, interdisciplinary, data products. This will require investment to build capacity and to adopt new technologies and approaches. This transition should be enabled by funders and policy makers. It should be embraced by research infrastructures and data repositories as a necessary evolution of their function and mission.

55 <https://eoscfuture.eu/data/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities/>

56 <https://preprints.arphahub.com/article/115047/>

57 Quistberg DA, et al. ‘Building a Data Platform for Cross-Country Urban Health Studies: the SALURBAL Study’. *J Urban Health*. 2019 Apr;96(2):311-337. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-018-00326-0>. PMID: 30465261; PMCID: PMC6458229.

58 INSPIRE PEACH is based on the OMOP Common Data Model, which provides for granular specification of data for reuse: <https://aphrc.org/inspire/project/a-platform-for-evaluation-and-analysis-of-covid-19-harmonised-data-peach-2/>

59 <https://oceaninfohub.org/odis/>

60 <https://www.gbif.org/>

9. Enable FAIR Practice in Research Communities

Technical standards that can communicate information about all aspects of data need to exist and be implemented, both at the level of domains **and** for the purposes of cross-domain exchange. Many research disciplines have developed technical standards for metadata, and these are to varying extents adopted. While some domains are well organised regarding metadata exchange, others rely on the organic emergence of good practices which remain relatively ungoverned or are dominated by the implementations of major infrastructure players. It is essential to enable research disciplines to develop data standards, to support their implementation, and to encourage good practice.

A singular feature of the WorldFAIR strategy and approach was to emphasise the importance of the role played by various stakeholders that can genuinely represent a research discipline, or a significant part of it. It is such organisations that can pose the question ‘how do we want our science to be conducted?’ and thereby articulate the wishes of a community. The WorldFAIR project was designed to involve a number of such organisations. Particularly important in this role are longstanding International Scientific Unions like IUPAC (founded in 1919), or emergent initiatives such as OneGeochemistry.

Similarly, those standards organisations that serve particular research communities (the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics [OHDSI] program in clinical medical research, the DDI Alliance in social, behavioural and economic sciences, etc.) as well as more general standards bodies serving broader needs (such as the W3C for Web standards) must be engaged.

The WorldFAIR project demonstrated the importance of a multi-stakeholder approach and the role that can be played by a number of different types of organisations and stakeholders

in advancing FAIR practice. Such organisations include: global infrastructures (GBIF, WPO9; ODIS, WP11); international representative and authoritative organisations (IUPAC, WPO3; OneGeochemistry, WPO5); data infrastructures (Sikt and ADA, WPO6; INSPIRE, WPO7); metadata standards organisations (IUPAC, WPO3; DDI, WPs 06, 07, 08; TDWG, WP 09 and 10; GloBI, WP10); and influential projects (NanoCommons, WPO4; INSPIRE, WPO7; SALURBAL, WPO8).

Recommendation 9.1: Enable standards bodies and international and representative organisations.

To advance FAIR implementation, it is important to take a multi-stakeholder approach. In particular, policy makers and funders should help support the role played by representative and authoritative organisations as well as standards bodies on an international scale.

Recommendation 9.2: Support WorldFAIR+.

The WorldFAIR approach should be further tested and refined as a means of enabling research communities to develop and implement good practice, through a multi-stakeholder approach. Policy makers and funders should support the WorldFAIR+ initiative and similar activities.

As recommended in the ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ report, “Research communities need to be supported to develop interoperability frameworks that define their practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and infrastructure.”⁶¹ Similarly, the UNESCO

61 European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Turning FAIR into reality: final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>; p.29.

Recommendation on Open Science calls on Member States and other stakeholders to promote “Community agreements, concluded in the context of regional or global research communities, and which define community practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, ontologies and terminologies, tools and infrastructure. International scientific unions and associations, regional or national research infrastructures and journal editorial boards each have a role to play in helping develop these agreements. In addition, convergence between the various semantic artefacts (particularly vocabularies, taxonomies, ontologies and metadata schema) is essential for the interoperability and reuse of data for interdisciplinary research.”⁶² The FIPs exercises undertaken by the WorldFAIR project are a useful approach to enable communities to articulate, reflect on, and evolve their practice. The FIPs approach will be more effective if it is conducted internationally at a global scale. Both CODATA (through WorldFAIR+ and its collaborations with the UN System and International Scientific Unions) and the Research Data Alliance (through its Communities of Practice) are well-placed to coordinate such activities.

Recommendation 9.3: Support the FIPs approach and infrastructure.

Funders and policy makers, through investment and appropriate policy direction, should support the global data stewardship community to socialise the FIPs approach, and to improve and sustain the necessary infrastructures.

Recommendation 9.4: Support CODATA and RDA to enable research communities.

The Research Data Alliance and CODATA should be supported in their activities to enable research disciplines and interdisciplinary research areas to advance their FAIR practices.

10. Support the Sustainability of Semantic Artefacts

Many of the organisations that develop and maintain specifications and standards are international and global in scope. These include treaty organisations like BIPM⁶³, large and well-resourced standards organisations like the Open Geospatial Consortium⁶⁴, as well as smaller entities serving particular domains, like the DDI Alliance⁶⁵ or TDWG⁶⁶. Some International Scientific Unions like IUPAC⁶⁷ have a particular vocation to establish and maintain standards and terminologies. Some of these entities are well-financed. Others rely extensively on volunteer effort, or time donated by researchers and data experts. Although such activities can be extremely effective, they are often significantly under-resourced, particularly when the passion of creating a resource gives way to the more mundane (and less visible) task of maintaining it. The challenges involved in maintaining or transitioning technical platforms, handing over leadership, or simply of financial sustainability are present for many such initiatives. Such entities have a wide range of business models, governance arrangements and juridical statuses.

Standards such as Schema.org⁶⁸, DCAT⁶⁹, SKOS⁷⁰, PROV-O⁷¹, and DDI-CDI⁷² are recommended in the draft CDIF. These have a number of different

62 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, VI.iii.18.f, p. 24. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

63 <https://www.bipm.org/en/>

64 <https://www.ogc.org/>

65 <https://ddialliance.org/>

66 <https://www.tdwg.org/>

67 <https://iupac.org/>

68 <https://schema.org/>

69 <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

70 <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

71 <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

72 <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

origins and maintainers, but the prominence of Web standards developed and maintained under the auspices of W3C is notable. The stability and sustainability of standards included in the CDIF will be important, and a matter of interest for EOSC and other stakeholders internationally.

The availability of funding to ensure the further development of such entities, even when they are outside the EC (on the model that led to WorldFAIR) would be extremely beneficial to European research and to EOSC. If international funding partnerships can be agreed, similar in ambition to the Belmont Forum, to assist data and metadata standards development, so much the better; but the EC has the capacity and mission to lead the way. One immediate step could be a survey and analysis of business models, governance and juridical statuses along the lines of the study CODATA previously conducted with OECD on 'Business Models for Sustainable Data Repositories'⁷³.

Recommendation 10: Support the Sustainability of Semantic Artefacts.

Policy makers and funders should help to ensure the sustainability of the standards organisations that develop and maintain metadata schema, terminologies, and other semantic artefacts. An immediate step would be to fund a project to conduct survey and analysis of business models, governance and juridical status, and make recommendations to improve the sustainability and effectiveness of such organisations.

⁷³ OECD (2017), "Business models for sustainable research data repositories", OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 47, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/302b12bb-en>

11. Strengthen International Partnerships

True to its remit and mission, the WorldFAIR project takes a global view and insists that the EC, the European Research Area, and EOSC have a major role to play as part of an international science ecosystem. It is not a mere truism to observe that science is a global endeavour, with global ramifications. Similarly, standardisation efforts — particularly in science, data and metadata — need to be global. It is firmly in the interest of the EU, and essential to the success of EOSC, to contribute positively to international data infrastructures and standards development.

Therefore, the creation of partnerships with authoritative international organisations or initiatives is a necessary part of building EOSC and should not be neglected. To avoid building a silo, EOSC should avoid the temptation to 'go it alone'. On the contrary, EOSC should actively partner with existing international data infrastructures and organisations that maintain standards and metadata schema (particularly those related to the UN data ecosystem), with inter-governmental initiatives and with global representative bodies such as the International Science Council and the International Scientific Unions. The Research Data Alliance and CODATA have important roles to play to assist with the internationalisation of EOSC activities.

Recommendation 11: Strengthen International Partnerships.

EOSC should actively build international partnerships with standards bodies, inter-governmental initiatives and global representative bodies. Contributing to the development of a strong global ecosystem for data and metadata exchange will benefit EOSC and is necessary for its success.

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